

D1.3 Report and main conclusions of the biowaste collection

Grant agreement
number 818312

Report and main conclusions of the biowaste collection

Deliverable 1.3. | VALUEWASTE Project | Grant agreement number 818312

Work Package No	1
Work Package Title	Selective collection of urban biowaste – Pilot experience
Work Package Leader	Prezero
Issue Date	30/09/2022

VALUEWASTE's partners

Disclaimer and acknowledgements

"This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No. 818312"

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Document Information

Acronym	VALUEWASTE
Title	Unlocking new VALUE from urban bioWASTE
Grant Agreement Number	818312
Call	H2020-SFS-2018-1
Project Coordinator	Asociación Empresarial Centro Tecnológico De La Energía Y Del Medio Ambiente De La Región De Murcia (CETENMA)
Document Type (R/DEM/DEC/OTHER)	R
Dissemination Level (PU/CO/CI)	PU

DOCUMENT HISTORY

Issue	Date	Comment	Author
V1	30/09/2022		Prezero

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VERIFICATION AND APPROVAL

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Approval Final Deliverable by Coordinator	30/09/2022	CETENMA

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Executive summary

One of the main challenges of urban biowaste management is to integrate a valorisation system in a city context, and to recover strategic products with a market value that offsets the global cost of biowaste valorisation.

To implement successful urban biowaste valorisation schemes to produce high value products with attractive and sustainable business cases, it is imperative to feed the processes with high quality biowaste in sufficient amount. This relies on efficient and successful biowaste selective collection systems which are scarce in Europe.

This deliverable gathers the main insights of the pilot biowaste selective collection experience carried out in Murcia (Spain) in the VALUEWASTE project. The experience was performed from the end of February 2020 to April 2022 targeting two main types of customers: citizens and large producers of biowaste. The collected biowaste was transported to Murcia's waste pre-treatment plant where it was converted into proteins and biofertilizers following the VALUEWASTE project valorisation scheme.

The results obtained during the biowaste collection experience evidence that to achieve a successful biowaste collection, it is necessary to follow a specific process which is described in this report. We believe that this experience is useful in terms of replication by providing measures with recommendations and suggestions for the future implementation of biowaste valorising schemes. The process starts by deciding which day to launch the selective collection of biowaste in the selected area. Once that day has been chosen, there are a series of actions before and after that day.

The experience gained in this pilot experience will be used for the extension of the selective collection in the entire municipality of Murcia.

The actions proposed in this deliverable have been discussed and evaluated with other relevant stakeholders, resulting in the development of a CEN Workshop Agreement ("[Key factors for the successful implementation of urban biowaste selective collection schemes¹](#)"), which is publicly available and can be found as an Annex to this document.

¹ Link: https://www.cencenelec.eu/media/CEN-CENELEC/CWAs/RI/cwa17866_2022.pdf

1 Objectives

This deliverable provides an assessment of the biowaste collection experience, including conclusions and recommendations for future applications. And for that, it was considered useful to explain all the actions developed for the selective collection of organic waste implemented at pilot scale in the municipality of Murcia. In this way, this report has a clear replication focus.

These actions include the development of the plan, the definition of biowaste, the method of serving the different types of customers, and can be divided as those that have been carried out before the start of the selective collection of biowaste (pre-planning) and after this date.

From February 20 to April 22, the pilot test of biowaste collection was carried out. 2 different types of customers have been selected for this pilot test: citizens and large biowaste producers.

The citizens come from the neighbourhood of La Flota, and the large producers are food shops and restaurants from other areas. The initial scope of the pilot experience was as follows:

- Citizens: La Flota, 8,087 inhabitants.
- Large producers: 264 food shops in 8 closed markets.
- Large producers: 170 restaurants in the city centre area.

However, as explained in detail in the following chapters, this project has been affected by COVID-19, so there have been changes in the initial scope of the project. This is for example the case of restaurants, which did not participate in the project.

2 Steps to follow before starting the collection (pre-planning, M1-M15)

Pre-planning is crucial to the success of a biowaste collection experience. Aspects not considered in this phase are very difficult to change in the next phase, which is when the biowaste collection service begins.

Planning for biowaste collection begins with knowing the waste streams in a community, determining the sources, quantities, and characteristics of biowaste in the area in question.

2.1 What is biowaste?

Before starting, it is important to provide a clear definition of what is biowaste and what is not. Biowaste includes biodegradable garden and park waste, food and kitchen waste from households, restaurants, caterers and retail premises, and comparable waste from food processing plants.

In the VALUEWASTE project biowaste has been defined as:

- Fruit and vegetables scrap.
- Cooked food leftovers.
- Eggshells, shellfish, and nuts.
- Coffee grounds and infusions.

An effective communication campaign should explain what a biowaste is and which fractions should not be managed in a biowaste collection (non-required material, NRM), like:

- Dirty paper towels and napkins.
- Wipes.
- Diapers
- Pet excrement.
- All the waste that must go to light packaging bin, paper bin, glass bin and mixed fraction bin.
- Although it is a biowaste, pruning and vegetable waste should not be introduced into the collection point as its volume and different composition affects the subsequent treatments to be carried out. This waste should be collected using another collection system.

The main characteristic of biowaste is that it typically occupies little volume, has a high amount of water and if the temperature is high, it decomposes quickly generating leachates and odours (which is a recurrent issue in hot places like Murcia).

Biowaste generally has a low level of porosity; this makes it a material with a low degree of compatibility. If compacted, a large amount of leachate can be generated.

The density of the biowaste that is deposited in the biowaste bin depends on its quality. The NRM that are usually in the biowaste bin are paper and cardboard, plastic bags, and plastics. These materials have very low density, so the more improper materials with these characteristics (NRM), the lower the density of the biowaste. Therefore, it is important to know the density of the biowaste for two main reasons:

- to know the filling rate of the biowaste bins, avoid overflows and determine the minimum frequency of emptying these bins.
- to correctly size the volume of the facilities where the biowaste is going to be treated.

From the experience in the VALUEWASTE project, the average density of biowaste from citizens has been around 450 kg/m³ and that of large producers 650 kg/m³. This density has been measured at the waste treatment plant. Results are provided in table 1.

In terms of quality, measured as the percentage of NRM in the biowaste, in the VALUEWASTE project an average of 3% for large producers and 14% for citizens has been observed. More information and details are provided in the chapter about quality of the biowaste.

Table 1: Density of the biowaste 9/3/2021 was raining and the biowaste was too wet. This data has not been considered.

Customers	day of week	date	kilos	volume	kg/m ³
citizens	Tuesday	02/03/2021	1320	3,3	400
citizens	Wednesday	03/03/2021	1360	3	453
open market + citizens	Thursday	04/03/2021	4140	8	518
citizens	Friday	05/03/2021	1380		
citizens	Saturday	06/03/2021	1240	4,2	295
	Sunday	07/03/2021			
citizens	Monday	08/03/2021	2280	4,4	518
citizens	Tuesday	09/03/2021	1490	2,4	621
citizens	Wednesday	10/03/2021	1320	3	440
open market + citizens	Thursday	11/03/2021	5620	9,9	568

2.2 Amount of biowaste in the mixed fraction

It is important to know which is the amount of biowaste in the mixed fraction for the same reasons mentioned when speaking about density. There are two ways to know the amount of biowaste in the mixed fraction:

1. Selecting the biowaste from each type of customer and taking samples of these. This way is more expensive but more accurate. When taking samples, the seasonality of the biowaste must be considered, so the characterizations of the mixed fraction must be carried out, at least, for each of the seasons of the year (spring, summer, autumn, and winter). This characterization is normally carried out at the treatment centre where the mixed fraction is taken.
2. Other more economical option is to use existing data on biowaste composition assuming that it reflects the reality.

The VALUEWASTE project used 33 historical data from 2015 to 2020 of waste analytics from the municipality of Murcia (Case b, Figure 1: Evolution of the percentage of biowaste in the mixed fraction from 2015 to 2020.)

Figure 1: Evolution of the percentage of biowaste in the mixed fraction from 2015 to 2020

A difference in the composition of biowaste is observed depending on the season of the year. During spring and summer, the amount of biowaste is higher due to the higher number of fruits and their higher water content compared to autumn-winter. See figure 3.

Figure 2: variation of biowaste in the mixed fraction depending on season of the year.

According to the information, the amount of biowaste in the mixed fraction that has been considered for the VALUEWASTE project was 41% of the total waste (average 2015-2020 samples). However, it must be bear in mind that there is a future trend towards a decrease in biowaste.

2.3 Biowaste KPIs

Two parameters have been used as KPI in VALUEWASTE project, a quantity parameter that anticipates the level of participation in the project, and a quality parameter that measures the amount of NRM that is collected.

2.4 KPI Quantity

Once the amount of biowaste in the residual fraction is known, the next step is to define a Key Performance Indicator (KPI) for quantity:

KPI = % of biowaste collected over total biowaste.

The measurement of this KPI of quantity during a period will be given by the data provided by the scales of the waste treatment centre and the estimation of biowaste contemplated according to the analysis of the mixed fraction.

This KPI should be established for the different types of customers, in the VALUEWASTE case, citizens and large producers, separating if it is possible both collections if there are weighing systems in the collection vehicle or if the biowaste is collected by different vehicles.

This indicator provides information on the percentage of participation in the selective collection of biowaste.

Although the VALUEWASTE project sets a daily collection amount of 4-5 tons, it is more realistic to collect 3.89 tons of biowaste per day depending on the daily production per customer type and participation expected. See table 4

The data Kg waste per day come from a study carried out by the TRAGSA Consultancy on the selective collection of organic waste in the Community of Murcia.²

Table 2: maximum tons of biowaste depending on the participation expected

2.5 KPI Quality

Another KPI which must be also analyzed is the quality KPI for biowaste. This measurement is carried out by taking a sample of biowaste when the vehicle arrives at its destination:

KPI = amount of biowaste in the sample (kg)/ Total sample (kg).

A high quality biowaste at source helps to obtain a high value raw material for the processes at VALUEWASTE value chains in the waste treatment plant. Therefore, from the beginning of the project, quality has been analysed.

2.6 Customer types

There are two types of customers for biowaste: citizens and large producers. They are differentiated by the amount of biowaste they generate. If a customer generates more than 10 liters of biowaste per day, it is considered as a large producer of biowaste.

A large producer customer generates a higher quality biowaste than a citizen. Thus, it is a priority to incorporate this type of customer (food stores, open markets, restaurants) into a selective biowaste collection experience.

²Link:[http://www.carm.es/web/pagina?IDCONTENIDO=48665&IDTIPO=11&RASTRO=c852\\$m1463,53799](http://www.carm.es/web/pagina?IDCONTENIDO=48665&IDTIPO=11&RASTRO=c852$m1463,53799)

2.6.1 Citizens

The pilot test of selective collection of biowaste for citizens has been carried out about La Flota. The situation of La Flota neighbourhood in Murcia municipality is showed in *Figure 3: location of neighborhood of La Flota*. This neighbourhood has a population of 8,087 inhabitants and there are 62 businesses that can be assimilated to large producers (*Table 3: name, location of large producers and type of business* and *Table 4: number of inhabitants per stree*).

For the design of the biowaste collection service, it is important to know this information, especially those associated with large producers. These data were provided by Murcia City Council.

Table 3: name, location of large producers and type of business

name	Tipo Via	Address	Type of business
	CALLE	ALMIRANTE CHURRUCA	Bakery
	Calle	ALMIRANTE CHURRUCA	Bar
	Calle	ALONSO DE OJEDA	nursery school
	Calle	ALONSO DE OJEDA	Food to take away
	Calle	ALONSO DE OJEDA	Bar
	Calle	ANTONIO DE ULLOA	butcher's shop
	Calle	ANTONIO DE ULLOA	Supermarket
	Paseo	CIENTIFICO GABRIEL CISCAR	Bar
	Paseo	CIENTIFICO GABRIEL CISCAR	bar

Table 4: number of inhabitants per street

TIPO VIA	STREET NAME	NUMBER	COMMUNITY NAME	HABITANTS
CALLE	ALCALA GALIANO	1	EDF. MARIN	2
CALLE	ALCALA GALIANO	1	EDF. MARIN	1
CALLE	ALCALA GALIANO	1	EDF. MARIN	4
CALLE	ALCALA GALIANO	1	EDF. MARIN	6
CALLE	ALCALA GALIANO	3	EDF. MARIN	1
CALLE	ALCALA GALIANO	3	EDF. MARIN	1
CALLE	ALCALA GALIANO	3	EDF. MARIN	1
CALLE	ALCALA GALIANO	3	EDF. MARIN	1
CALLE	ALCALA GALIANO	5	EDF. MIRTO	4
CALLE	ALCALA GALIANO	5	EDF. MIRTO	1
CALLE	ALCALA GALIANO	5	EDF. MIRTO	2
CALLE	ALCALA GALIANO	5	EDF. MIRTO	2
AVDA	ALICANTE	1		1
AVDA	ALICANTE	1		6

Figure 3: location of neighborhood of La Flota

2.6.2 Large Producers

Restaurants

This type of customer has not participated in the VALUEWASTE project due to COVID-19 restrictions during 2020 and 2021. The proposal for the collection of biowaste made for this type of customer was to provide them with a small 60–90-liter bin to be kept on their premises and placed on the public street at the time of collection. This proposal was not accepted by the restaurant owners due to hygienic reasons and because they had no space to store this bin.

They proposed that a biowaste bin like the one for citizens be placed next to their usual collection point on the public road (Figure 4: location for restaurant bins). The bin for restaurants can be seen in Figure 5: biowaste bin for restauration.

Figure 4: location for restaurant bins

Figure 5: biowaste bin for restauration

Within days of placing the bins for the restaurants, they were closed for 3 months due to Covid restrictions. While the VALUEWASTE project was progressing, there were no stable conditions to start the collection of biowaste for restaurants again.

Closed markets

Figure 6: closed market

Table 5: number of vendors in each closed market

	2019	2022
Plaza de Verónicas	149	71
Plaza de El Carmen	41	17
Plaza Vistabella	27	28
Plaza Cabezo de Torres	9	12
Plaza de La Alberca	16	12
Plaza de San Andrés	13	12
Plaza de Espinardo	9	5
	264	157
variation		-41%

The VALUEWASTE project includes collection from closed markets,

Figure 6. It is important to consider that due to the global economic situation, there has been a significant decrease in the total number of vendors served between the beginning of the project and the end, see Table 5.

It is also worth noting that due to COVID-19 a large part of the goods sold have been presented covered with plastic film, considerably reducing the amount of biowaste deposited into the biowaste bins in grocery stores and fruit shops.

To size biowaste collection, it is important to know the number of vendors and the type of biowaste they generate. This information has been provided by Murcia City Council. See Table 6.

Table 6: number of vendors per closed market and type of activity

Ayuntamiento de Murcia Plazas de Abastos			Censo de Plaza Cabezo de Torres jueves, 6 de junio de 2019	
Nº	NIF	TITULAR	ACTIVIDAD	FechaConces.
001			SALAZONES	
002			FRUTOS SECOS	
003			FRUTOS SECOS	
004			FRUTAS Y VERDURAS	
005			FRUTAS Y VERDURAS	
006			FRUTAS Y VERDURAS	
007			PESCADOS	
008			PESCADOS	

Open markets

Figure 7: Thursday open market

This type of customer was not foreseen to be included in the VALUEWASTE project. As a contingency action and since restaurants did not participate in this project, the open markets of the city of Murcia were added to VALUEWASTE. These markets are usually held once a week and sell a large quantity of fruit and vegetables. See Figure 7: Thursday open market

The quality of the biowaste is very good and what is not biowaste (NRM) is easily separated in the trommel of the sorting facility (cardboard and large plastics). This type of customer produces high quantity and quality of biowaste, and less human and material resources are needed for its collection. For this reason, incorporating this type of customer into a biowaste collection plan is a priority.

To dimension the collection correctly, it is necessary to know the number of vendors. See Table 7: *number of vendors in Santa M^a de Gracia open market.*

Table 7: number of vendors in Santa M^a de Gracia open market

Ayuntamiento de Murcia
Servicio de Plazas y Mercados
C/ Selgas, 1, 2^a planta
30001 Murcia

Censo de Santa M^a de Gracia

jueves, 6 de junio de 2019

Nº	M	Licencia	NIF	TITULAR	ACTIVIDAD	Reserva
002	9				ROPA ORDINARIA	
003	3				DROGUERIA Y PERFUMERIA	
004	8				TEJIDOS	
006	7				CHARCUTERIA	
007	6				FRUTAS Y VERDURAS	
008	4				ROPA ORDINARIA	
009	6				FRUTAS Y VERDURAS	
010	4				FRUTAS Y VERDURAS	
011	4				ROPA ORDINARIA	
012	4				ROPA ORDINARIA	

The total number of vendors was 44 in Santa María de Gracia (Location 1) and 107 in La Fama (Location 2).

Figure 8: location of open markets in the city of Murcia

2.7 Proposed location of collection points

After knowing where the main biowaste producers are in the different areas, collection points are established. Biowaste collection points should be placed next to the customer's usual waste collection point.

One of the most important factors for citizens to participate in the separate collection of biowaste is the distance between their home and the collection point. Long distances discourage participation. On the other hand, the more collection points there are, the higher the cost of the service. Therefore, the variables number of bins and distance must be analysed.

In the VALUEWASTE project, the following criteria for locating biowaste bins were followed:

- a. For large producers, at the usual place where they deposit their waste.
- b. For citizens, the first objective of a biowaste recycling scheme is to incorporate those who are already recycling other waste, so locate the biowaste collection point next to the current collection point for recyclable waste (packaging, paper, glass). This measure also helps to improve the quality of biowaste.
- c. Once point b) is completed, biowaste collection points can continue to be placed at the remaining collection points where biowaste is generated and always previous demand of the customer.

The proposal for the location of collection points determines the resources to be used by the biowaste collection service. In VALUEWASTE project, the location of biowaste collection points has followed criteria a) and b).

2.7.1 Large producers

Closed markets

Figure 9: (left) location of closed market biowaste collection point; (right) Biowaste bin for closed markets.

Location of the collection point next to the customer and the type of bin is shown in Figure 9: (left) location of closed market biowaste collection point; (right) Biowaste bin for closed markets.

2.8 Characteristics of the collection points

The collection point is important because it is the meeting point between the customer and the collection service. It should have its own identity. This site must be sized to accommodate all biowaste generated by customers. The frequency of biowaste collection will therefore affect the storage capacity of the biowaste at the collection point.

It is advisable to visit all the large producers in the area to find out the quantity and type of biowaste they generate and thus determine more accurately the volume of biowaste to be collected.

2.8.1 Citizens and closed markets

At VALUEWASTE, the Murcia City Council decided that for aesthetic reasons the biowaste bin to be installed should be of the same model as those existing in the municipality of Murcia.

The biowaste bin installed is a side-loading bin with a useful capacity of 2,000 liters. It has an RFID (Radio Frequency Identification) chip so that all collections are recorded when the bin is emptied.

In the case of having several waste fractions at the collection point, it is advisable not to place the biowaste bin at the end of the collection point. This increases the quality of the biowaste because it prevents the customer from depositing their waste at the first bin to which they have access.

The following order is recommended: mixed fraction, organic, packaging, paper, and glass, i.e., the bin that generates odour on one side and that which does not generate odour on the other. This order should be respected whenever possible. In this way the customer gets used to always having the biowaste collection point in the same place, avoiding errors when depositing the biowaste (see Figure 12: *type and location of biowaste bin*, circle red is where biowaste bin is).

Figure 12: type and location of biowaste bin

Depending on the type of customer to be served (large producer or citizen), the opening of the lid where the biowaste is deposited must have different characteristics. The size of the lid of the element to deposit biowaste is a critical factor to obtain better biowaste quality. The larger the size of the lid, the poorer the quality of the biowaste.

For collection points on public street, it is advisable to differentiate two types of lids:

- **Citizen**, lid of no more than 25 x 25 cm.

Figure 13: citizen lid

- **Large producer**. This lid is opened with a key previously delivered to the waste-generating establishment. It is recommended that the bin has a mechanical system which, when pressed by the foot, opens the lid of the bin. One of the main complaints of large biowaste producers is that they need to hold the bag with both hands due to its weight to deposit the biowaste into the bin and they cannot open the lid at the same time.

Figure 14: large customer lid

At the beginning of the project there were two types of biowaste bins, one with a large lid of 40x40 cm for large producers and other of size 20x20 cm for citizens. See Figure 15: *evolution in bin design*.

There were locations in La Flota where both producers deposited biowaste. If a citizen-type lid container was placed, the large biowaste producer could not deposit the biowaste because of the size of the lid. If a large producer container was used, the biowaste was contaminated probably from the municipal waste channel.

As it was not possible to place two types of bins in the same location, the design of the container was changed with a lid that could be used for both types of customers. The large producer would open the lid with a key and the citizen would have a small lid to deposit his biowaste.

Figure 15: evolution in bin design

Use of underground biowaste bins

As biowaste is quite heavy, it is advisable to keep the height of the discharge lid as low as possible, especially for large producers. Underground biowaste bins make it easier for large producers to deposit biowaste. The biowaste bin has been replaced by an underground one in closed markets of Vistabella and El Carmen, increasing the amount of biowaste collected by 25% in El Carmen and 40% in Vistabella and generating less odours. See *Figure 16: replacement of the street bin with an underground bin.*

Figure 16: replacement of the street bin with an underground bin

It is possible to use a rear-loading biowaste storage system and deposit biowaste in a side-loading system. In this way two different routes do not pass through the same place, avoiding noise and saving fuel. This has been the case in the Saavedra Fajardo market (closed market), where the small bins are from the customer and are taken to the side-loading bin where the biowaste is deposited on the street.

The mechanical system installed in the side-loading bin (Ale-Hop) facilitates the tipping of the small bin.

Figure 17: Alehop System

2.9 Open markets.

Figure 18: bin used for open market

As a rule, the more biowaste a customer generates, the closer the collection point should be to the customer. The Murcia open market has been the largest producer of biowaste. Because it is a market that is held only one day per week, the bins must be placed and removed on that day.

The bins placed are rear loading bins with four wheels and a capacity of 800 liters (Figure 18). The fact that they have wheels has been a great advantage because the retailer could move the bin to his work area and deposit all the biowaste there.

2.10 Parameters which are important for the calculation of the collection cost

Once the study of the population, the collection points, the type of bin and the current waste collection systems have been carried out, it is time to find out the cost of implementing the new service.

It is desirable to have the same waste collection system than the municipality already must optimize resources for collection, washing and maintenance of bins. Therefore, if the current collection systems are working properly, it is normal that the new biowaste collection will be done with the same system as the existing one.

Collection costs will be optimized due to economies of scale and staff will already be trained in the operation of the new equipment. The factors to be considered when designing the biowaste collection service are:

2.10.1 Type of collection vehicle

- The type of vehicle is conditioned by the type of bin in which the biowaste is to be collected.
- The size of the streets will determine the size of the vehicle to be used.
- If the system chosen to collect the biowaste is side loading, it is necessary to consider the presence of tree branches, streetlights, etc. in the location of the collection point.

Due to the high density of biowaste, it is not necessary to compact the biowaste. However, it is necessary for the vehicle to have a hydraulic system to lift the bin and move the waste out of the vehicle tipping the waste.

It is advisable for the vehicle to have GPS and, if the investment allows it, automatic bin weighing. Having these two tools allows the route to be optimized and the efficiency of the service to be improved.

2.10.2 Number of vehicles to be used

This is linked to the frequency of collection and the number of bins to be collected.

2.10.3 Collection frequency

This is one of the parameters that more influences the collection cost. In the case of biowaste, especially for citizens' bins, the limiting factor is not the filling of the bin, but the odours and possible health problems generated by the decomposition of the biowaste due to high temperatures. Therefore, an agreement must be reached between all stakeholders to establish the frequency of biowaste collection. The higher the frequency, the less health problems but the higher the cost. And the other way round, the lower the frequency, the more health problems but the lower the cost.

Is it possible to reduce the frequency of the mixed waste fraction, and increase it for the biowaste bin? The answer is yes if the mixed waste bin is not full of waste and with waste around it at the time of collection. This is normally achieved if there is a high level of citizen participation in the selective collection program for light packaging, paper, cardboard, and glass which reduces the volume of waste in the mixed waste bin.

Therefore, the cost of the biowaste service is also linked to the response of citizens to recyclable waste that occupies a larger volume in the mixed waste bin.

The limiting factor in the collection of biowaste is time. The maximum number of biowaste bins to be emptied per working day depends on:

- Time from leaving the facility to the first bin.
- Time from first bin to last bin.
- Time from last bin to waste plant or transfer plant.
- Time from waste plant or transfer plant to arrival at facilities.
- Rest time.
- Time to solve possible incidents.

With all these factors it is possible to estimate the budget of biowaste collection.

2.11 Communication to stakeholders of the initial planning

Once the customers, the location of the collection point, its characteristics, and the economic cost of the biowaste collection service have been studied, it is essential to involve the interested parties in the decision to be taken.

For the VALUEWASTE project, the main stakeholders are:

- **Customers:** representation of citizens and large producers.
- **Technicians:** Staff responsible for collection services (regional, municipal, and private companies' technicians).
- **City managers:** Environmental and economic departments from the municipality and politicians.

Non-participation at this stage may mean that after starting the biowaste collection service, there is no participation from customers or no budget to address the separate collection of biowaste. All stakeholder suggestions should be listened to.

It is important the presence of a person who serves as a mediator between all the stakeholders and who seeks the common interests of all of them.

At this stage, if needed, it is probably necessary to consider updating the municipal legislation on waste collection, establishing the obligation to separate waste. The date of the change of the legislation must be set before starting the collection of biowaste.

In VALUEWASTE, because it has been a pilot test, the City Council has not changed the municipal legislation regarding the obligation to separate biowaste.

2.12 Customer communication process

Customer's participation is crucial to the success of a biowaste collection scheme. It is important to check the citizen's opinion before starting the biowaste collection service. The best tool for this is to carry out surveys in the street and online (participatory process of the City Council, image 28). These surveys should also be carried out with large producers.

Figure 19: portal of the City Council

Surveys should include the following information:

- a. Customer data: Type of customer, age, occupation, address, email. It is important to get the customer's email address. It is the basis to continue to be informed when the biopatrols disappear from the area.
- b. What do I do to minimize climate change? For example:
 - Reduce, reuse, recycle,
 - Reduce water consumption,
 - Reduce plastic consumption,
 - Sustainable purchasing,
 - Use of renewable energies.
- c. Do I currently separate waste? which ones? why?
- d. Are you willing to separate and deposit biowaste at the collection point? If not, please specify why not.

- e. What environmental benefits can be obtained from biowaste?
- f. Questions or suggestions.

The customer must previously accept the privacy conditions of the survey and it is advisable that the information is hosted on the portal of the City Council.

In VALUEWASTE a total of 2,580 surveys were carried out via the participation portal of Murcia City Council. Of these surveys, 2,470 were from the La Flota neighbourhood, far exceeding the expected response. The characteristics of the sample are:

Figure 20: different types of customers by age

Figure 21: different works by age

Figure 22: ages of citizens that made the survey and living status

Answers of the survey

The aim of the survey was to find out the current level of recycling in the La Flota neighbourhood and why people do or do not recycle. The questions are shown in the figures included in the next pages, including a comment on the main outputs right below the figure.

Figure 25: answers of the survey - glass, paper, or packaging separation

Results: most of the citizens recycle other waste like paper, glass, and packaging

Figure 26: answers of the survey - reasons to separate waste

Results:

- Reasons for recycling: environment, social responsibility.
- Citizen's think is not mandatory to recycle, although it is.
- It is not easy recycling.
- Little known about circular economy.

Figure 27: answers of the survey - measures against climate change

Main measures against climate change:

- reduce, reuse, and recycle,
- reduce plastic consumption
- reduce water consumption.

Figure 28: answers of the survey - why not to separate

Why NOT to separate

Reasons	YES	Total
Containers are far	36	36
I do not know how to do it	5	5
I don't have enough space at home / premises	51	51
I don't want to know anything about it	8	8
It won't make any difference if I rate it or not	19	19
No customer service	13	13
Traditional collection service is enough	6	6
Total	138	138

Main reasons not to separate:

- not enough space at home and
- bins far from my house.

Another objective was to determine the citizen's knowledge of biowaste.

Figure 29: answers of the survey -what benefits for the environment can we get from biowaste?

Results:

- Main use of biowaste is for improving soil quality.
- Some knowledge that can be used to produce energy.
- No knowledge that can be used as a feed or may have new applications in the future.

Impact of the survey on the communication campaigns

All the information received through the surveys was used to plan the content of the communication campaign in the following terms:

- Most citizens were already familiar with the recycling process, so the campaign focused on incorporating a **new type of waste**, biowaste.
- The **social and environmental reasons** for recycling biowaste were emphasized.
- It was explained **how to separate** organic waste at home. Every visitor to the customer service centre in La Flota was given a bin to deposit biowaste. At the same time, they were invited to do the survey if they had not done it before.
- The **circular economy** concept was incorporated into biowaste management.
- Recycling biowaste is good for **climate change**.
- It was explained that in addition to the traditional uses of biowaste (compost, energy) there were other **new alternatives** that were one of the objects of VALUEWASTE (obtaining insect protein and nutrients from biowaste).

When to start a campaign is a critical issue, if it starts early it is forgotten, if it starts late, it does not reach the customer. The start of an awareness campaign should not be timed to coincide with events that diminish its effect, such as local holidays, Christmas, the start of school, etc. So it was decided to start the campaign after Christmas (January-20). This campaign had to be interrupted in mid-March 20 because all non-essential activities were paused due to COVID-19.

More detailed information on how the citizen information campaign was carried out is described in Annex A.

3 Prestart of biowaste selective collection

Before starting the collection, it is advisable to inspect the pilot areas with the vehicle that will be collecting biowaste and check that there are no problems, e.g., with the width of the streets or the future location of the bins. This route should be done at the time/shift when the collection will take place. The objective is to anticipate these potential problems before the biowaste bins are on the street.

Figure 30: Actions before start of collection

The day on which the biowaste collection service starts is an important day. If all of tasks mentioned in Figure 30 have not been considered, the quantity and quality of the biowaste may be compromised. And making changes is much more complicated at this stage of the project than at the previous one.

As it has been discussed, communication is key. More detailed information on how the citizen information campaign was carried out (customer communication process) in the VALUEWASTE project is described in Annex A. This campaign had to be paused in mid-March 20 because all non-essential activities were cancelled due to COVID-19.

From the start of the biowaste collection, the project must be monitored using the quantity and quality KPIs discussed above. The evolution of these two parameters will determine the actions to be taken in the future.

The actions to be carried out at this stage must have the appropriate technology for an intelligent management of the information. This is the technology used during this project related to collection.

3.1 Technology used for collecting biowaste

Figure 32: TAG

There are two essential elements that can provide information about the service: the bins and the vehicles. Regarding bins, it is important to know where they are, when they are collected, washed, and repaired, and how much biowaste they contain when they are collected.

Each bin is provided with unique container identifier sensor or transponder (TAG, Figure 32). The

TAG provides information on the type of container, the commercial brand, the volume, the age of the container. This type of sensor is very reliable. TAG readers have been also used to identify container washings and repairs.

Figure 31: manual TAG reader

Concerning vehicles, the following technologies have been applied in the VALUEWASTE project:

1. **GPS.** All the vehicles are equipped with this technology. They are always active and the driving pattern of the drivers who collect the biowaste (acceleration, braking, maximum speed, etc.) are analysed.

Figure 33: GPS Route

Figure 34: RFID TAG reader

2. **RFID TAG reader.** Every time a biowaste container is lifted, the date, time, TAG, and position are recorded. With this information it is known how often the bins are lifted.

- 3. Weighing system.** Each time a container is emptied, the system does two weights, one when the bin is full of biowaste and the other when is empty. The difference between the two situations is the net weight of the biowaste.

The weighing is associated with the TAG so that the kilograms of biowaste in each container are known at all times. It is important to bear in mind that the accuracy of this system is not as reliable as the weight scale at the treatment centre.

This tool is important for managing communication campaigns once collection has started. By analysing the data, action is taken in those places where the contribution of biowaste is lower than expected. These data were analysed monthly.

Figure 35: Software for weighing System at the vehicle

All the information related to the bins and vehicles is managed by means of specific software which, based on a database, allows reports to be drawn up. See *Figure 36: information available using software* and *Figure 37: data base information*.

Figure 36: information available using software

Figure 37: data base information

VEHICLE	FAMILY	date	WEIGHT	TAG	AREA	STREET
5003	Recolector Carga Lateral 13 M3 Drchas	03/03/2022 17:49	25,00	0040000003436E7A	2200 Orgánica Contener F	Vistalegre Avenida Marqués de Los Vélez
5003	Recolector Carga Lateral 13 M3 Drchas	03/03/2022 17:56	5,00	0040000003436E5E	2200 Orgánica Contener F	La Flota Calle Antonio Ulloa
5003	Recolector Carga Lateral 13 M3 Drchas	03/03/2022 17:59	15,00	0040000003436E59	2200 Orgánica Contener F	La Flota Avenida de la Marina Española
5003	Recolector Carga Lateral 13 M3 Drchas	03/03/2022 18:01	30,00	0040000003436E70	2200 Orgánica Contener F	La Flota Avenida de la Marina Española
5003	Recolector Carga Lateral 13 M3 Drchas	03/03/2022 18:10	5,00	0040000003436E77	2200 Orgánica Contener F	La Flota Avenida Almirante Loaysa
5003	Recolector Carga Lateral 13 M3 Drchas	03/03/2022 18:16	5,00	0040000003436E6F	2200 Orgánica Contener F	La Flota Calle del Navegante Juan Fernández
5003	Recolector Carga Lateral 13 M3 Drchas	03/03/2022 18:17	25,00	0040000003436E83	2200 Orgánica Contener F	La Flota Calle del Navegante Juan Fernández
5003	Recolector Carga Lateral 13 M3 Drchas	03/03/2022 18:20	20,00	0040000003436E7D	2200 Orgánica Contener F	La Flota Calle Almirante Churruga
5003	Recolector Carga Lateral 13 M3 Drchas	03/03/2022 18:26	15,00	0040000003436E84	2200 Orgánica Contener F	La Flota Avenida de Victoria
5003	Recolector Carga Lateral 13 M3 Drchas	03/03/2022 18:30	60,00	0040000003436E68	2200 Orgánica Contener F	La Flota Calle de Alonso de Ojeda
5003	Recolector Carga Lateral 13 M3 Drchas	03/03/2022 18:32	50,00	0040000003436E6D	2200 Orgánica Contener F	La Flota Calle del Pintor Salvador Dalí
5003	Recolector Carga Lateral 13 M3 Drchas	03/03/2022 18:34	15,00	0040000003436E5F	2200 Orgánica Contener F	La Flota Calle del Pintor Salvador Dalí
5003	Recolector Carga Lateral 13 M3 Drchas	03/03/2022 18:36	10,00	0040000003436E88	2200 Orgánica Contener F	La Flota Paseo Virgen de la Fuensanta
5003	Recolector Carga Lateral 13 M3 Drchas	03/03/2022 18:38	40,00	0040000003436E71	2200 Orgánica Contener F	La Flota Avenida de Victoria
5003	Recolector Carga Lateral 13 M3 Drchas	03/03/2022 18:46	20,00	0040000003436E7B	2200 Orgánica Contener F	La Flota Calle del Músico Antonio Rodríguez de Hita
5003	Recolector Carga Lateral 13 M3 Drchas	03/03/2022 18:48	10,00	0040000003436E78	2200 Orgánica Contener F	La Flota Calle del Obispo Fray Antonio Trejo
5003	Recolector Carga Lateral 13 M3 Drchas	03/03/2022 18:55	130,00	004000000340B563	2200 Orgánica Contener F	Vistabella Calle Casas de los Periodistas
5003	Recolector Carga Lateral 13 M3 Drchas	03/03/2022 19:08	280,00	0040000003436E82	2200 Orgánica Contener F	San Pedro Calle de Plano de San Francisco

4 Start of biowaste selective collection

The main operational activities related VALUEWASTE have been the collection of the biowaste and the washing of the biowaste bins.

4.1 Biowaste bin washing

Biowaste bins are washed externally and internally by a pressurized water equipment. The washing takes place after the collection service and the washing frequency is twice a week in winter and four times in summer. It is advisable to double the washing frequency in the hottest months because high temperatures decompose biowaste more quickly, producing odours and leachate and customer complains.

Figure 38: washing biowaste bins

4.2 Biowaste collection

During the selective collection experience the following biowaste tons were collected:

- Total biowaste: 930 tons.
- Citizens and closed markets: 727 tons.
- Open markets: 203 tons.

The next graph (Figure 39: total biowaste collection (April-21 to April-22)) shows the evolution of biowaste collected during the last year. During the last year there has been a slight upward trend (black dotted line).

Excluding the summer vacation season, biowaste collection is between 45 and 54 tons per month.

Figure 39: total biowaste collection (April-21 to April-22)

That represents an average of 1,6 tons of biowaste per day.

KPI Quantity of the project % = $1,6/3,8 = 42\%$. (see Table 4, Maximum tons of biowaste expected).

For those 1,6 tons on average per day, 0,4 are for the open markets and the rest for citizens, large producers of La Flota and closed markets. This data come from the scale at the waste treatment plant. The analysis of the deviations will be discussed in chapters 4.4.2 and 4.4.3.

4.2.1 Biowaste collection service in close markets, large producers, and citizens

Biowaste is collected daily, except on Sundays and public holidays. The route takes place between 2 p.m. and 8:30 p.m. and is 121 km long. See Figure 40: biowaste route and details of the route (data from the side loader vehicle, time, and distance). The number of km is high due to the dispersion of closed markets. The collection service was optimized by using a 2-axle collection side loader vehicle.

Figure 40: biowaste route and details of the route (data from the side loader vehicle, time, and distance)

Figure 41: Vehicle used for citizens and closed markets (side loader)

The evolution of the amount of biowaste collected from the beginning of the project to the end for citizens and closed markets is shown below

Figure 42: tons of biowaste per month (citizens and closed markets)

Table 8: biowaste collected per type of customer

Type of customer	% of biowaste
citizen	63%
large producer	8%
closed market	29%

Using the vehicle weighing system when the container is emptied, 63% of the waste comes from the citizens, 29% from the closed markets and 8% for other large producers (fruit shops, scholar canteens, etc). These data are from the last month of the project.

The KPI for the citizens of La Flota is below:

- Total amount of biowaste: $8.087 \text{ inhabitants} \times 0.96 \text{ kg/waste per day} \times 41\% \text{ biowaste} = 3.183 \text{ kg}$
- Daily amount of biowaste collected in La Flota: $1.200 \text{ kg} * 63\% = 756 \text{ kg}$
- $\text{KPI} = 756/3183 = 24\%$

This KPI is lower than packaging, paper and glass collections (32%, 40% and 45% respectively). The percentage of participation for packaging, paper and glass has been calculated using the same technology (weighing system of the truck).

This route has had a biowaste collection performance of between 200 and 300 kilograms per hour.

Citizens generate biowaste every day, fruit shops 6 days a week and canteens 5 days a week. The average weight per bin and per day in VALUEWASTE are next:

Table 9: amount of biowaste per type of customer and bin

average weight per bin per day (kg)	
Citizen	27
large producers	14

Figure 43: Scholar canteens users

The scholar canteens (large producers) have the peculiarity of being closed during school vacations and they do not generate biowaste at this time. There are two types of scholar canteens, those that prepare the food in their own kitchen and those that bring it in through a catering service. To get more biowaste, the first case is interesting. In the second case, the amount of biowaste is smaller, sometimes there is no biowaste because they optimize the amount of food and demand. Of the four schools chosen to participate in this project, only one had its own kitchen, and this is the reason the biowaste production data of the large producers was lower than that of the citizens.

Therefore, our recommendation is that fruit shops, butchers, fish shops and all those restaurants or establishments that have their own kitchen must be incorporated into a biowaste collection program.

4.2.2 Biowaste collection service in open markets

This route runs every Thursday. It takes between 3 and 4 hours and runs for 55 km. the route starts at our facilities (red circle), goes to the two markets (green circle) and deposits the biowaste at the VALUEWASTE demo site (brown circle).

Figure 44: Route for open market and data from this route, duration 3 h 24 min, distance 55 km.

The vehicle used for collecting the open market is shown in Figure 45 and the evolution of the amount of biowaste collected from jan-21 to the end of the project is shown in Figure 46.

Figure 45: Vehicle used for open market collection

Figure 46: tons of biowaste per month (open market)

This route has had a biowaste collection performance of between 800 and 1000 kilos per hour. It is therefore a priority to incorporate this type of customer into a selective biowaste collection program.

Seasonality is observed in graph 60. Biowaste increases in spring and early summer due to the higher amount of fruit and the fact that high temperatures can degrade this biowaste.

The quality of the biowaste is very high (see Figure 48). It is possible that some biowaste bins may be quite heavy and more than one worker will be needed to move them to the biowaste collection vehicle (see Figure 47).

Figure 48: biowaste from open market

Figure 47: the bins are difficult to be moved if they are full

4.3 Quality of the biowaste

Figure 49: measuring biowaste quality

For the determination of the %NRM, the average size of the sample is 200kg and the procedure comes as follows:

- When the biowaste reaches the treatment plant, it is deposited on the ground.
- A caterpillar moves the biowaste and separates approximately 20% of it.
- From this sample, what is biowaste and what is not biowaste is separated, weighing both.
- % NRM is calculated as $\% \text{ non-biowaste} / \text{sample weight}$

Two periods of waste samples have been carried out:

- From the beginning of the collection until September 2020 (M16-M23), 107 samples
- Between January and June 2021 (M27-32), 41 samples.

Figure 50: samples from April-20 to oct-20

Figure 51: samples from Jan-21 to Jul-21

The amount of non-biowaste deposited in the bins has gone from 4.9% to 10% during these two periods (% Not required Material, NRM).

The percentage of NRM has been increasing over time as the amount of biowaste collected has increased. So, the more customer participation in the project, the less quality of the biowaste.

The quality of biowaste from large producers, especially open markets, is significantly better than that of citizens.

Large biowaste producers have a %NRM in the range of 2-4% (visual inspections) while citizens have had an MRW percentage that can triple large producers' figure.

It is recommended to always start a biowaste collection experience by talking about the quality of the biowaste. A customer who starts off with a bad biowaste selection process will be difficult to change in the future.

From the beginning, the bio-patrols (Staff whose mission is to interact with the customer, usually in a face-to-face mode) have informed the customer of what is biowaste and what is not.

5 Analysis of the evolution of the biowaste collection experience

5.1 Before the start of biowaste collection.

The following graph represents the percentage of selective collection in weight (paper, glass, packaging, biowaste) from 2011 to July-2022 over the total amount of waste collected in Murcia. See Figure 52.

The red bars represent the beginning and end of VALUEWASTE project. Year 2019 features the highest rate of selective collection over total waste (11,79%), From this year, even including biowaste collection, this percentage has decreased to 11,64% (2020), 11,62% (2021) and 10,90% (until July-2022).

Figure 52: Yearly evolution (%) of the selective collection over total waste from 2011 to 2022

The monthly trend between Feb-20 and Jul-22 can be seen in the graph 67. When biowaste collection started, the ratio was that 11,5% of the total waste was collected separately. When the collection finished, this figure has dropped to 10,4%. We do not know the causes of this decrease: lower consumption? change of habits due to Covid? Lack of interest of the citizen? What is certain is that the VALUEWASTE project started when the recycling rates began to fall after almost 10 years of uninterrupted growth.

Figure 53: Monthly evolution of the selective collection over total waste from beginning to end of VALUEWASTE

5.2 Biowaste collection scenarios

According to the data collected, we can distinguish three different scenarios for this project as showed in Figure 54:

Figure 54: Monthly amount of biowaste collected (citizens + large producers)

5.2.1 Scenario 1 (blue circle):

- At the beginning of march-20, the biowaste collection starts.
- Fifteen days later, due to COVID-19, the face-to-face communication campaign stops. All non-essential activities are stopped, so bars and restaurants are closed, and citizens stay at home. Bins for the restaurants are removed from the street. This situation continues until mid-June.
- During June, July and August 20, citizens leave the city of Murcia (holiday season).

Table 10: Kg of biowaste per day

Etiquetas de 1	Suma de 1st period
citizen	629
large producer	
closed market	100
Total general	729

At this stage, the participation is low, 20 tons per month- KPI Quantity is 20%. Most of the biowaste comes from the citizen. The large biowaste producers' campaign has not been completed due to COVID-19. Using the weighing system of the vehicle, the data is shown in Table 10.

The biowaste has the following characteristics:

- Very low percentage of NRM, less than 3%.
- Most of the plastics bags are biodegradable.
- High percentage of vegetables and fruits.

Figure 55: first day of collection

The communication process with the citizen was as follow (for more information about this process, see annex A):

- Letter from the Major.
- Communication through press, radio, TV
- Starting face to face communication with the citizen (less than 10 days of this action because of lockdown for Covid).

5.2.2 Scenario 2 (red circle):

- The communication campaign starts again in mid-September-20. The citizens' contribution increases.
- In autumn 2020 the restaurants are asked to participate. They do not accept it because they have other more serious issues to solve, and the contingency plan is carried out (see below).
- In January 21 the collection of biowaste is extended to the open market (1 day a week). The maximum amount of waste is reached and continues to be maintained with seasonal variations until the end of the project.

Contingency plan.

- 1. After summer 2020, a visual inspection of the biowaste bins was made for one week to count the number of bags of biowaste in each bin and to check the quality of the biowaste.**

There were 5 bins (marked with red cross in the picture below, Figure 56) that had less than 5 bags of biowaste per day. As there were other similar bins near them, they were removed from their locations and placed in 3 school canteens, 1 supermarket and a fruit store (see Figure 57)

Figure 56: Bins that were removed from La Flota neighbourhood

Figure 57: New location of bins (fruit shop and scholar canteens)

Figure 58: biowaste bin for supermarkets

As a result of this action, 145 kilos of biowaste are added daily, mainly from the fruit store and the school with its own kitchen.

In this neighbourhood, a biowaste container was placed next to two supermarkets. A few days after its placement, it had to be removed due to the presence of people who took the biowaste from this container before being emptied by the vehicle. The supermarkets did not want this to happen in front of their front door)

Other supermarkets that we wanted to join the VALUEWASTE project gave us the same reason for not participating before starting biowaste collection.

Table 11: Kg of biowaste per day

Etiquetas de	Suma de 2nd period
citizen	750
large producer	145
closed market	370
Total general	1265

Using the weighing system of the vehicle the amount of biowaste per day during this scenario is shown in the next table:

2. La Flota neighborhood.

During this phase, a face-to-face communication campaign was conducted for large producers. See image 75. Details of the campaign can be found in Annex A. The amount of biowaste collected from the citizens of La Flota has increased from 629 to 750 kilos per day. This represents a KPI Quantity of 24%.

No more biowaste bins have been placed on the street, five have even been removed in this phase. The increase in kilos is probably due to the continuation of the face-to-face campaigns by the biopatrols from mid-September.

Figure 59: fruit shop and School Canteen added to VALUEWASTE Program

3. New biowaste bin in two areas.

It was decided to place the bins foreseen for restaurants in two areas further away from the city centre to verify the response of citizens in this type of area. The chosen areas have been part of La Alberca and El Palmar (see Figure 60). The number of participants is 1.100 inhabitants. The biowaste collection service in these two areas started mid-October-21 (M36) and 15 biowaste bins were located at these areas. The objective of this measure is to know which is the response of citizens in areas far from the city centre.

Figure 60: location of biowaste bins in El Palmar (2 streets) and La Alberca (2 streets)

In these two areas, participation has been very low. Face to face campaigns have not been so intense as in La Flota's neighborhood. Also, the recycling rates of other waste fractions are lower than in La Flota.

The number of bags of biowaste was between 0 and 7 per bin per day, with an average of 3 bags. The quality of the biowaste was low as 1/2 of the bags inspected were not biowaste. The awareness campaign was conducted over two days. No large producers were on those streets.

5.2.3 Scenario 3, brown circle:

In this scenario the collection of biowaste is following a stable pattern with respect to the amount of biowaste:

- It decreases in the summer, during the vacation season.
- It increases during holidays (Christmas, local holidays, etc.), linked to the activity of the citizens.

Regarding large producers, it follows a pattern similar to that of the citizens. It should be noted that in the spring more biowaste is collected due to the characteristics of the product sold.

In this scenario, biopatrols only communicated with large producers. Citizens must contact them through social networks. Communication should be as personalized as possible.

With the surveys carried out at the beginning of the collection, 865 emails were obtained from citizens interested in this project. These citizens should be informed of the evolution of the project. To continue informing citizens, a QR code has been placed on all the bins.

Figure 61: QR code

The objective of this action is:

- Explain to citizens what we do with their biowaste.
- Report on the amount of biowaste that is contributed to each bin of this project

The link of this QR code offered the following information:

- Explanatory video about what PREZERO Murcia does after collecting the biowaste.
- Information about citizen contribution at each collection point.

Regarding the quality of the biowaste, although no analysis has been done in the last part of the project, it has decreased (visual inspection).

Therefore, it is necessary to always maintain an active campaign about biowaste quality. When this issue is no longer mentioned, the citizen relaxes and more NRM appear in the biowaste.

6 Main conclusions of the VALUEWASTE project

The results obtained during the biowaste collection experience evidence that to achieve a successful biowaste collection, it is necessary to follow a specific process as the one described in this report. We believe that this experience is useful in terms of replication by providing measures with recommendations and suggestions for the future implementation of biowaste valorising schemes.

The process starts by deciding which day to launch the selective collection of biowaste in the selected area. Once that day has been chosen, there are a series of actions before and after that day.

The previous actions are very important. Mistakes in this phase can mean moving away from the established objectives or even not being able to carry out the project. Actions to be taken before and after the launching day can be summarized as follows.

Before starting the collection, we highlight:

Quality and quantity parameters (KPIs) must be established. Quality must be present from the first communications. Trying to change the way in which a customer recycles if there is no biowaste quality may imply that he/she abandons this project.

The rates of participation in VALUEWASTE have been lower than expected:

- Citizens participate less in a biowaste program scheme than in other recycling schemes (paper, light packaging and glass).
- If the bins are located at the street, it is difficult to reach more than 30% of participation. If participation is to be greater, door-to-door collection should be encouraged.
- Restaurants did not participate due to the lockdown of their activities because COVID-19.

Prioritize the selective collection of biowaste to get more quantity and quality in the next order:

1. Offer this service to large biowaste producers. These are going to give more quality and quantity than the citizens. The quality of this biowaste must be controlled where it is generated.
2. Incorporate to the new biowaste collection those citizens who already recycle other types of waste. For this, the biowaste container should be placed next to the bins of other selective collections (packaging, paper, glass, etc.). The quality of biowaste from citizens is difficult to control at source (unless the collection of biowaste is door to door). It is advisable that the lid where the biowaste is deposited into the bin is not larger than 25x 25 cm.
3. If there are customers who wish to participate in a biowaste collection project and do not meet the above two requirements, providing collection service to this customer will be conditioned by negotiating with the customer a minimum biowaste container fill rate.

Once these steps have been taken, it is necessary to **estimate the costs** of the collection service according to the priorities mentioned above. The frequency of service and the number of collection points are the two most important variables in the cost of the service. Follow the order mentioned above (1,2,3) to establish the costs of the different services.

With the service proposals and costs, it is time to meet with the **stakeholders** to listen to them and present the proposals. It is possible that these meetings will result in new proposals. A commitment to stakeholder participation is essential. It should be the objective before starting the selective collection.

Adapt the **municipal legislation** on biowaste collection, establishing the obligation to separate biowaste.

Participatory processes via web or face-to-face interviews are important to know the citizen's perception of the new service. This information will serve to maintain communication with customers after the start of the selective collection. It is advisable to try to create a database of customers who are interested in selective collection.

After starting the biowaste collection:

The project should be analysed according to the KPIs mentioned above. **Work with KPIs** and not with expectations.

The **use of technology** in the collection vehicles (GPS, RFID, weighing systems, etc.) facilitates the task of obtaining these KPIs more easily.

All customers must be informed of their performance. Be **transparent** with them.

For **deviations** from these KPIs:

1. in large biowaste producers, it is necessary to make visits by bio-patrols (face to face interaction).
2. for citizens, establish communication hotlines. Better small news with high frequency than big news with low frequency.

All the actions mentioned in this deliverable have been discussed with other companies, organizations, and municipalities to create a CEN standard: Key factors for the successful implementation of urban biowaste selective collection schemes, CEN Workshop Agreement 17866 from Sept-22. This CWA is in Annex B

Annex A: Key actions for a successful communication campaign associated to the implementation of biowaste collection schemes

Before biowaste collection starts.

The following sections establish how to manage the communication process with the customer.

Letter from the Mayor

The mayor is the highest representative in a municipality, so it is recommended that the project of the new biowaste collection is announced by him/her (credible source of information, personal interaction) through an official letter.

The purpose of this letter is to involve the customers in the new project.

It is advisable that this letter is delivered to each home/business in the area. This delivery also serves to get to know the area better and know the number and type of customers. If a database of customers in the area is not available, this section is mandatory.

This letter should include the following information:

Figure 62: sending letter from the Major.

1. It should be explained that there is going to be a new biowaste collection point in the area.
2. That we should avoid wasting food and that biowaste that are not usable should go to home composting (if possible) and if not to the biowaste collection point.
3. It must be explained why this new service is going to be carried out:
 - a. Environmental reasons: circular economy, climate change, use of resources.
 - b. Legal reasons: European Regulations.
4. It is necessary to explain what is going to be done with this biowaste after it has been collected and to set objectives.
5. It is advisable to explain what is going to happen in the next few days:
 - a. Face to face communication with customers (biopatrols).
 - b. Establishment of a meeting point for doubts, indicating where it will be located and its timetable.
 - c. It is necessary to clarify which are the channels of communication in case of doubts: free hotline, social media...
6. We must thank all the customers of the area for their collaboration, making them participants of what their collaboration contributes.

Details of how to separate biowaste, where the collection point is, etc

Communication through press, radio, TV, social media. From the general to the particular.

Reliance on traditional media alone does not change behaviours unless you have personalized communication. Therefore, focus all messages on personalizing them as much as possible.

It is advisable to start with the mass media (press, radio, TV) and then move on to more personal media (website, social media, etc.).

The advertising campaign must unify all the elements of the biowaste collection to be easily recognizable by the customer. These elements are:

- Image of the collection point.
- Printed communication.
- Verbal communication: slogans, radio, TV
- Merchandising: collection buckets, magnets, etc.

Figure 63: Image of the biowaste bin

Figure 64: printed communication.

Figure 65: merchandising, bucket (left) Figure 66: merchandising, magnet (right)

In the messages the following information should be reported:

- That we all generate biowaste.
- It is the waste that we produce the most by weight.
- That we cannot continue to exploit nature and the collection of this waste comes to solve this issue. Link it with circular economy.
- What is biowaste and should go to the collection point and what is not biowaste.
- Advice on how to separate in the home/business.
- What is done with the collected biowaste.

Face to face communication, from the particular to the general.

This is the most important part of the communication process. The goal is to reach those customers who have doubts to adhere to separating their biowaste. The aim is that by the time citizens are informed, most of them already know about the new collection of biowaste because they have already been informed by their children or by the large producers or by the community around them.

The communication process should be carried out by the biopatrols, staff who will inform to the different types of customers. The communication process in each area starts from the particular to the general:

- **Schools and institutes.**
- **Large producers.**
- **Associations in the neighbourhood.**
- **Municipal services operating in the neighbourhood.**
- **Citizens**

Communication process in schools in the area.

The pupils should be informed about the separation of biowaste in the schools in the area. What these children learn will have a double effect as they will remember what they learn at home and help educate their parents and other family members. Students should be taught the words and definitions used in biowaste, so that over time all customers will speak the same language.

The following actions are recommended:

- Provide the schools with bins of the colour that identifies the collection point for biowaste in the different classrooms of the school.
- If there is the possibility of composting at school, then activities should be carried out in this respect.
- Messages to be launched for students:
 - Include biowaste in the health programs that schools usually have.
 - Encourage local consumption of biowaste and bring it to the collection point.
- The process of communication to schoolchildren should be repeated annually, always choosing the same school year to ensure that all pupils have received the training over time.

Figure 67: talk to students

Talk to students

Communication process to large producers.

According to the general to specific communication approach, large producers such as food markets, restaurants, bars, shops, etc., should be visited before the general campaign to the citizen. These are the customers who are going to produce the best quality of biowaste, so special personalized attention shall be devoted to this customer.

It is advisable to design a survey model for this type of customer. It should be similar to that of the citizen.

It is important to consider that there is no specific model of bin for the large producer to deposit the biowaste within their facilities. Each type of large producer must check for the bin that best suits their business.

Due to the amount of biowaste they generate and that this waste is heavy:

- No bags with biowaste weighing more than 20 kilograms should be lifted. If they generate more than that amount, they must be distributed in several bags with the maximum weight indicated.
- It should be made as easy as possible to ensure that the height of the biowaste dump at the collection point is as low as possible. With these criteria, the use of underground bins is appreciated by this type of customers as they have a low height to deposit the waste while preventing access to this type of waste once it has been deposited.
- If the collection point is on the public street, it is advisable to provide it with a lock so that the citizen does not contaminate the biowaste. Therefore, each large producer must be given a key to open the item at the collection point.

Recommended messages for large producers:

Figure 68: talk to large producer (closed markets).

- Public markets as the heart of biowaste.
- Circular economy, the biowaste you recycle returns as a new product to the market.
- If they participate in the separation of biowaste it can be made a line of advertising through social networks, stickers in shops, etc. It is important to take this step if there is commitment and reality of recycling, so you must negotiate with these customers when to give them publicity. For example, when the collection point is at 50% capacity. Giving large producers publicity before they have achieved their targets can be a disincentive for this type of project.

Associations in the neighbourhood

These customers are, for example, cultural associations, senior citizens' clubs, women's associations, and neighbourhood meeting centres.

Associations are the gateway to citizens and in general it is easier to reach an association than a citizen, requiring fewer resources for the same task.

It is often the case that an association expects something in return for their participation. Therefore, if they get involved, they should be rewarded. The reward should be linked to biowaste (a compost bin, bins for the household, visits to the waste plant, etc.).

Figure 69: La Flota senior citizens' association

Training for municipal services in the area.

These services comprise cleaning, collection, gardening, police services and others. Once the collection service has started in the area, they can inform the customer of incorrect behaviour, so they have to be trained in:

- What is a biowaste?
- When this biowaste is collected.
- How this waste is deposited.
- What is done with this biowaste after it is collected.

These are very basic questions, but if they do not know how to answer them, it gives an image of disorganization at the municipality.

These operators must be informed of the communication channels established with customers (free hotline, social media, etc.) in case they do not know how to respond to customer concerns.

Citizens

The citizen is the most numerous customers in each urban area, so they can provide a large amount of biowaste. The quality of the biowaste is more difficult to control, especially if the collection point is at the sidewalk, so the biopatrols should emphasize the message about how to obtain quality biowaste.

With this type of survey, previous information is obtained about what the customer thinks, an expected percentage of participation and we will have a database with the customer's emails for future communications. This is the information that will be used mainly to communicate with the customer after starting the biowaste collection service. If this information is not available, part of the follow-up of the next phase will not be possible.

There are two main motivations for citizens to recycle:

- Internal: they are usually environmental in nature and are stable over time. Thus, biopatrols must interact with customers through this type of motivations.
- External: they are usually economic. These motivations usually decrease when the economic incentive stops working.

Biowaste separation starts at home. According to VALUEWASTE surveys, the main reason for not separating biowaste at home is not finding the right space for biowaste separation.

One way to help in this regard is to deliver a bin to each household to deposit biowaste. Its characteristics are:

- No more than 10 litres if the biowaste is collected daily.
- It should be accompanied by a pack of biodegradable plastic bags. A quality biowaste is advisable to go inside this type of plastic.

Biopatrols should advise on how to place this bin at home and what goes into it. The delivery of this bin involves a great logistical effort, so it is advisable that the bin is delivered at the meeting point established in the area. This point will be attended by the biopatrols, and its timetable will depend on the activity in the area.

At the time of delivery of the bin, the survey mentioned above will be made. If the customers do not want to do it at that moment, they will be told that they can do it whenever they want through the City Council's portal, indicating the web address.

The citizen's bin serves to motivate the citizen to take the survey.

Once the process has been completed, the bin collection areas should be analysed. If the number of bins delivered in an area is low, it is advisable to carry out a visit by the biopatrols in that area and, if necessary, create a temporary bin drop-off point for that area.

Communication with the customer at this level is established by building or business.

The messages that should be launched for this type of customer are:

- Avoid food waste.
- Message: "everything that comes out of the earth returns to the earth".
- What is biowaste and what is not biowaste.
- Importance of the biodegradable bag.

Figure 70: Biopatrols informing to citizens at information point in La Flota.

Figure 71: Bucket as a gift.

Communication After Biowaste Collection Starts

Steps to follow after starting the collection

The day on which the biowaste collection service starts is an important day. If all the above has not been considered, the quantity and quality of the biowaste may be low. And making changes is much more complicated at this stage of the project than at the previous one.

From this day on, the project must be monitored using the quantity and quality KPIs explained above.

The evolution of these two parameters will determine the actions to be taken in the future.

The actions to be carried out at this point must have the appropriate technology for an intelligent management of the information, based on the information obtained in the surveys prior to the collection. These actions come as follows:

1. Face-to-face actions

During the first week from the start of collection it is necessary for the biopatrols to establish face-to-face communication interaction with the customer to find out if they are participating in the separation of biowaste and, if they are not, to find out the reasons why.

At those collection points where there is a low quality and/or quantity of biowaste, the biopatrols should follow up to check the causes of the deviation. Information on the quality and quantity at the different collection points should be transmitted from the collection service to the biopatrols. There needs to be fluid communication between the collection and the awareness service.

2. Establish a meeting point

Inform the customer of the existence of a meeting point in their neighbourhood and its opening hours. Normally it will coincide with the one in the previous phase.

3. Conducting surveys

In this phase, surveys should be carried out to analyse the degree of acceptance of the new service. These surveys should be carried out when the amount of biowaste collected has stabilized and will serve to gather new ideas with which to relaunch the selective collection of biowaste.

Surveys may be physical if biopatrols are in the area or using information contained in the database from previous surveys. The contents of the surveys should focus on:

- Degree of acceptance of the new service. It is necessary to know if the customer continues to recycle biowaste.
- If it does not continue, know why.
- What improvements would be necessary to incorporate more customers to this service?

4. Customer service hotlines

Due to economic reasons, the presence of biopatrols in the targeted area should be reduced as collection progresses. Their presence will only be necessary in those areas where the expected quantities/qualities are not achieved.

The use of personalized communication technologies is essential at this stage of the project. Based on the information collected in the street by the biopatrols and the previous surveys, it is necessary to create a database of customers so that they are informed of the evolution of the project. An informed customer is a more participative customer.

Examples of best practices related to customer service are:

- To have its own website for biowaste, a website of active listening where you learn from customers. This website must be simple, resolve doubts and be linked to social networks.
- Use of social media:
 - We must try to keep the project alive. Create a lot of small news informing about the day to day of the project. It is better a lot of small news than a few big ones.
 - If there are influencers in the area, it is interesting to contact them to add them to the project.
- Place a QR code at each biowaste collection point. This point leads to a web address where the customer is informed of the following:
 - Evolution of the quantity collected in the area and, if possible, at the collection point.
 - Quality evolution.
 - What is being done with the biowaste after it is collected.
 - Survey on participation in the project.
 - Other comments.

This information should be updated monthly and must be transparent.

How to correct deviations

In any biowaste collection scheme, a contingency plan is necessary, especially if the results are not as expected for the two parameters considered: quantity and quality of the biowaste.

The communication process between the biopatrols and the biowaste collection service is essential. This collection service must inform at which service points there are quality and quantity deviations to the biopatrols. The following aspects should be considered in this plan:

- Monthly monitor during 6 months after D-Day the Quantity and Quality KPI's. If the expected results are achieved, follow up every three months.
- If there is a new need for more collection points in the area, consider eliminating those with little biowaste.
- If at a collection point non-required waste appears constantly and in appreciable quantity, this collection point must be eliminated if the causes of this deviation cannot be solved.
- Face to face communication (biopatrols) where there is deviation in quantity and/or quality. If not, inform the customer through social networks and website.
- It is necessary to consider whether the collection point is adapted to the customer's needs.
- Inform to the customers of their actions where there are quantity and quality deviations using information as personalized as possible.
- As new areas are added to the collection, it is advisable to maintain comparative indicators between them.
- It is advisable to organize visits to the plant where the biowaste is treated so that customers can see what is done with it. In areas where there is less quantity/quality of biowaste, these visits are necessary.

Annex B: CEN Workshop Agreement 17866 from Sept-22

CEN

CWA 17866

WORKSHOP

September 2022

AGREEMENT

ICS 13.030.40

English version

Key factors for the successful implementation of urban biowaste selective collection schemes

This CEN Workshop Agreement has been drafted and approved by a Workshop of representatives of interested parties, the constitution of which is indicated in the foreword of this Workshop Agreement.

The formal process followed by the Workshop in the development of this Workshop Agreement has been endorsed by the National Members of CEN but neither the National Members of CEN nor the CEN-CENELEC Management Centre can be held accountable for the technical content of this CEN Workshop Agreement or possible conflicts with standards or legislation.

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Ref. No.:CWA 17866:2022 E

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European foreword

This CEN Workshop Agreement (CWA 17866:2022) has been developed in accordance with the CEN-CENELEC Guide 29 “CEN/CENELEC Workshop Agreements – A rapid prototyping to standardization” and with the relevant provisions of CEN/CENELEC Internal Regulations – Part 2. It was approved by a Workshop of representatives of interested parties on 2022-06-17, the constitution of which was supported by CEN following the public call for participation made on 2020-09-01. However, this CEN Workshop Agreement does not necessarily include all relevant stakeholders.

The final text of CWA 17866:2022 was provided to CEN for publication on 2022-07-01.

Results incorporated in this CWA received funding from the European Union’s HORIZON 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement number 818312.

The following organizations and individuals developed and approved this CEN Workshop Agreement:

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Introduction

Every year each European citizen produces on average 200 kg of municipal biowaste. This means that between 118 and 138 million tons of biowaste arise annually in the EU. The municipal biowaste management systems that currently exist in Europe, such as landfilling, do not give a second life to materials or resources contained in the biowaste. Other alternatives such as incineration and composting do not allow to take full advantage of the biowaste potential.

With the increase in biowaste production, the EU's priorities are to reduce food waste, increase separate collection and reuse or recycling. One of the main challenges for biowaste management is to integrate a valorization system in a city context, and to recover strategic products with a market value that offsets the global cost of biowaste valorization.

Thus, the recovery and valorization of biowaste is one of the main lines of several EU-funded projects, like VALUEWASTE¹, which proposes an integrated system for urban biowaste valorization into key strategic products for the EU.

In order to implement successful valorization schemes to produce high value products with attractive and sustainable business cases, it is imperative to feed the processes with high quality biowaste. High quality biowaste relies on efficient selective collection systems and pre-treatments. Unfortunately, such systems to ensure high quality biowaste are scarce in Europe, making current valorization systems uneconomical and therefore underutilizing the potential of urban biowaste.

Standardization of the influencing key factors for the improvement of the selective collection and management of urban biowaste will help city managers and waste management service providers to increase the quality of the selectively collected biowaste, enabling the development of robust biowaste valorization processes. The influencing key factors will focus on actions to promote biowaste collection and improve the perception of citizens on urban biowaste as a local source of valuable materials.

Therefore, standardization will bring citizens' sorting and recycling efforts to increase the biowaste quality and contribute to pave the way for the transition of cities to a circular economy.

Part of this CWA is based on the biowaste selective collection experience implemented in the VALUEWASTE project. This research project has received funding from the European Union's HORIZON 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement number 818312.

¹) <https://valuewaste.eu/>

1 Scope

This CWA provides guidance for the implementation of biowaste selective collection schemes.

This CWA also paves the way to increase citizen engagement, as this is crucial for the successful implementation of urban biowaste selective collection schemes.

It is intended to be used by city managers and municipal waste managers with interest in implementing the selective collection of urban biowaste to produce high quality biowaste (i.e., minimal presence of non-required fractions) which can be then used in robust valorization processes with attractive business cases.

2 Normative references

There are no normative references in this document.

3 Terms and definitions

For the purposes of this document, the following terms and definitions apply.

ISO and IEC maintain terminological databases for use in standardization at the following addresses:

- ISO Online browsing platform: available at <https://www.iso.org/obp>
- IEC Electropedia: available at <https://www.electropedia.org/>

3.1

biowaste

waste that is composed chiefly of organic matter and typically comprises biodegradable garden and park waste, food and kitchen waste from households, restaurants, caterers and retail premises, and comparable waste from food processing plants

Note 1 to entry: For further information see Annex A.

3.2

non-required fraction

waste fraction affecting negatively the valorization process.

Note 1 to entry: For further information see Annex A.

3.3

customer

biowaste producer.

Note 1 to entry: In this CWA there are two types of customers: citizen and large producer.

3.4

collection point

place where the customer deposits the biowaste on public areas for collection

3.5

mixed fraction

this is the fraction of the waste where the biowaste is actually being deposited before the selective collection of biowaste begins

3.6**D-day**

day on which the selective collection of biowaste begins. All previous and subsequent planning is done in reference to this day

3.7**biopatrols**

staff whose mission is to interact with the customer, usually in a face-to-face mode. Their aim is to change customer attitudes to increase the quantity and quality of biowaste

4 General

This document sets out a methodology for obtaining high quality biowaste and is intended to be of use to those municipalities where separate collection of biowaste has not started and already have collection systems in place.

In order to achieve high quality biowaste there are short- and long-term objectives. The short-term objectives are oriented towards planning and implementation and include the development of the plan, the definition of biowaste, the method of serving the different types of customers and the destination of this biowaste after it has been treated.

There is no single programme that works for all areas. Each target area may have its own geographic and demographic identity, way of collecting waste, market requirements, and legal and financial constraints. For a biowaste collection scheme to be successful, all of these variables must be accounted and planned for.

In this document, the factors common to all areas will be analyzed. However, the market requirements and legal and financial constraints of a biowaste collection service are not within the scope. When implementing the biowaste collection, it is important to consider the associated costs, logistics and carbon footprint, which will be specific to each particular case.

The first decision to be taken is to decide the day on which the selective collection of biowaste begins in an area (D-day). From this day onwards, there are a series of actions that shall be carried out before (Clause 5) and after (Clause 6) this day.

Clause 7 establishes a contingency plan to correct the deviations which may arise in terms of quantity and quality of biowaste.

Clause 8 is a summary of the key factors for the successful implementation of urban biowaste selective collection schemes.

5 Steps to follow before starting the collection (pre-planning)**5.1 General**

Pre-planning is crucial to the success of a biowaste collection scheme. Aspects not considered in this phase are very difficult to change in the next phase, which is when the biowaste collection service begins.

Planning for biowaste collection begins with knowing the waste stream in a community, determining the sources, quantities and characteristics of biowaste in the area in question.

Before D-day and in the order sets out here, the following actions shall be carried out:

5.2 Biowaste typology

There are two ways to know the amount of biowaste in the mixed fraction:

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- a) Selecting the biowaste from each type of customer and taking samples of these. This way is more expensive but more accurate. When taking samples, the seasonality of the biowaste must be taken into account, so the characterizations of the residual fraction must be carried out, at least, for each of the seasons of the year (spring, summer, autumn and winter). This characterization will normally be carried out at the treatment center where the mixed fraction is taken.
- b) Other more economical option is to use existing data on biowaste composition assuming that it reflects the reality.

Once the amount of biowaste in the residual fraction is known, it is time to set a Key Performance Indicator (KPI) for quantity:

KPI quantity = % of biowaste collected over total biowaste

The measurement of this KPI of quantity will be given by the data provided by the scales of the waste treatment center and the estimation of biowaste contemplated according to the analysis of the rest fraction.

This index indicates the percentage of participation in the selective collection of biowaste.

This KPI should be established for the different types of customers: citizens and large producers, separating if it is possible both collections if there are weighing systems in the collection vehicle.

Another KPI which must be also analyzed, the quality KPI for biowaste. This measurement will be carried out by taking a sample of biowaste when the vehicle arrives at its destination and will be:

KPI quality % = amount of biowaste in the sample (kg)/ Total sample (kg)

5.3 Customer types

There are two types of customers for biowaste: citizen customer and large producer customer.

They are differentiated by the amount of biowaste they generate daily. An average house produces a volume of less than 10 litres of biowaste per day. If a customer generates more than 10 liters of biowaste per day, it is considered as a large producer of biowaste.

A large producer customer will normally generate a higher quality biowaste than a citizen. It is a priority to incorporate this type of customer into a selective biowaste collection programme.

5.4 Proposed location of collection points

Biowaste collection points should be placed next to the customer's usual waste collection point. To improve the quality of the biowaste, the priority is to place the biowaste collection point where there are other collection fractions such as paper, glass, packaging, etc.

The proposal for the location of collection points will determine the means to be used by the biowaste collection service.

5.5 Characteristics of the collection points

The collection point is important because it is the meeting point between the customer and the collection service. It should have its own identity.

This site must be sized to accommodate all biowaste generated by customers. The frequency of biowaste collection will therefore affect the storage capacity of the biowaste at the collection point.

It is advisable to visit all the large producers in the area to find out the quantity and type of biowaste they generate and thus determine more accurately the volume of biowaste to be collected.

The size of the lid of the element to deposit biowaste is a critical factor to obtain better biowaste quality. The larger the size of the lid, the poorer the quality of the biowaste.

It is therefore advisable to differentiate, if the collection point is on a public street, two types of lids of the biowaste into the collection element:

- Citizen, lid of no more than 25 × 25 cm.
- Large producer, closed lid of at least 40 × 40 cm. This lid is opened with a key previously delivered to the waste-generating establishment.

As biowaste is quite heavy, it is advisable to keep the height of the discharge lid as low as possible, especially for large producers. Underground biowaste containers make it easier for large producers to deposit biowaste. A reflection on the type of container is necessary, taking into account all technical, economical and ergonomic aspects.

In the case of having several waste fractions at the collection point, it is advisable not to place the biowaste collection point at the end of the collection point. This increases the quality of the biowaste because it prevents the customer from depositing their waste at the first bin to which they have access.

The following order is recommended: mixed fraction, organic, packaging, paper and glass. That which generates odor on one side and that which does not generate odor on the other. This order should be respected as far as possible. In this way the customer gets used to always having the biowaste collection point in the same place, avoiding errors when depositing the biowaste.

In addition, digital tools are needed to encourage and guide citizens. Examples of best practices related to customer service are provided in Subclause 6.5.

5.6 Communication to stakeholders of the initial planning

Once the customers, the location of the collection point and its characteristics have been studied, it is essential to involve the interested parties in the decision to be taken.

The main stakeholders in this project are:

- Customers.
- Technicians.
- City managers.

Non-participation at this stage may mean that after starting the biowaste collection service, there is no participation from customers or no budget to address the separate collection of biowaste.

All stakeholder suggestions should be listened to. Some may be accepted, some may not.

At this stage, if needed, it is probably necessary to consider adapting the municipal legislation on waste collection, establishing the obligation to separate waste. The date of the change of the legislation has to be set before starting the collection of biowaste.

5.7 Customer communication process

5.7.1 General

Customer's participation is crucial to the success of a biowaste collection scheme. The communication process must have the following characteristics:

- There must be a personal and direct interaction with the citizen.
- Actions must be creative and well designed.
- They must have the right technology for intelligent information management.

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There is resistance to shift to recycle biowaste so public attitudes and objections to biowaste recycling need to be identified.

There will be a proportion of customers who will participate in biowaste recycling regardless of the quality of the campaign or the recycling facilities. This type of customer is usually environmentally motivated. It is for this reason that a biowaste collection program should be linked to the municipal circular economy concept and strategy. This type of customer should be offered the possibility to participate in the communication process of the biowaste collection project.

On the other hand, there will be another proportion of customers who will not be willing to participate in this type of program, so the effort should not be focused on this group.

However, the majority of customers can be made aware through specific programs and it is to this segment that effort, knowledge and understanding should be dedicated.

To motivate these customers, the following considerations should be taken:

- The sources of information should be credible and come from relevant reference groups.
- Recommendations made should be related to beliefs and practices accepted by the individual.
- The information should raise awareness through the communication of the negative impacts associated to traditional management schemes, and, at the same time, inform about the advantages of the new proposed approach.
- The information should provide specific recommendations.

Prior to the starting of the collection service, it is important to know the degree of customer acceptance of biowaste collection. This issue will be addressed later through the surveys.

In order to know the customer of an area in advance, it is recommended to use information that is normally in the databases of the City Councils:

- How many customers are there?
- what kind of customers are there in the area?
- what is the age of the customers?
- income from customers?
- Do they have experience in recycling other waste fractions?

When to start a campaign is a critical issue, if it starts early it is forgotten; if it starts late it does not reach the customer.

The start of an awareness campaign should not be timed to coincide with events that diminish its effect, such as local holidays, Christmas, the start of school, etc.

It is recommended to always start by talking about the quality of the biowaste. Quantity will come later. A customer who starts off with a bad biowaste selection process will be difficult to change in the future.

The following subclauses establish how to manage the communication process with the customer.

5.7.2 Letter from the Mayor

The mayor is the highest representative in a municipality, so it is recommended that the project of the new biowaste collection is announced by him/her (credible source of information, personal interaction) through an official letter.

The purpose of this letter is to involve the customers in the new project.

It is advisable that this letter is delivered to each home/business in the area. This delivery also serves to get to know the area better and know the number and type of customers. If a database of customers in the area is not available, this section is mandatory.

This letter should include the following information:

- a) It should be explained that there is going to be a new biowaste collection point in the area.
- b) That we should avoid wasting food and that biowaste that are not usable should go to home composting (if possible) and if not to the biowaste collection point.
- c) It must be explained why this new service is going to be carried out:
 - Environmental reasons: circular economy, climate change, use of resources.
 - Legal reasons: European Regulations.
- d) It is necessary to explain what is going to be done with this biowaste after it has been collected and to set objectives.
- e) It is advisable to explain what is going to happen in the next few days:
 - Face to face communication with customers (biopatrols).
 - Establishment of a meeting point for doubts, indicating where it will be located and its timetable.
 - It is necessary to clarify which are the channels of communication in case of doubts: free hotline, social media...
- f) All the customers of the area should be congratulated for their collaboration, making them participants of what their collaboration contributes.

Details of how to separate biowaste, where the collection point is, etc. are shown in the following clauses.

5.7.3 Communication through press, radio, TV, social media. From the general to the particular

Reliance on traditional media alone does not change behaviors unless you have personalized communication. Therefore, focus all messages on personalizing them as much as possible.

It is advisable to start with the mass media (press, radio, TV) and then move on to more personal media (website, social media, etc.).

The advertising campaign must unify all the elements of the biowaste collection in order to be easily recognizable by the customer. These elements are:

- Image of the collection point.
- Printed communication.
- Verbal communication: slogans, radio, TV.
- Merchandising: collection buckets, magnets, etc.

In the messages the following information should be reported:

- That we all generate biowaste.

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- It is the waste that we produce the most by weight.
- That we cannot continue to exploit nature and the collection of this waste comes to solve this issue. Link it with circular economy.
- What is biowaste and should go to the collection point and what is not biowaste.
- Advice on how to separate in the home/business.
- What is done with the collected biowaste.

5.7.4 Face to face communication, from the particular to the general

5.7.4.1 General

This is the most important part of the communication process. The goal is to reach those customers who have doubts to adhere to separating their biowaste.

The aim is that by the time citizens are informed, most of them already know about the new collection of biowaste because they have already been informed by their children or by the large producers or by the community around them.

The communication process should be carried out by the biopatrols, staff who will inform to the different types of customers.

The communication process in a given area starts from the particular to the general:

- 1) Schools and institutes.
- 2) Large producers.
- 3) Associations in the neighborhood.
- 4) Municipal services operating in the neighborhood.
- 5) Citizens.

5.7.4.2 Communication process in schools in the area

The pupils should be informed about the separation of biowaste in the schools in the area.

What these children learn will have a double effect as they will remember what they learn at home and help educate their parents and other family members.

Students should be taught the words and definitions used in biowaste, so that over time all customers will speak the same language.

The following actions are recommended:

- Provide the schools with bins of the color that identifies the collection point for biowaste in the different classrooms of the school.
- If there is the possibility of composting at school, then activities should be carried out in this respect.
- Messages to be launched for students:
- Include biowaste in the health programs that schools usually have.
- Encourage local consumption of biowaste and bring it to the collection point.

- The process of communication to schoolchildren should be repeated annually, always choosing the same school year to ensure that all pupils have received the training over time.

5.7.4.3 Communication process to large producers

According to the general to specific communication approach, large producers such as food markets, restaurants, bars, shops, etc., should be visited before the general campaign to the citizen. These are the customers who are going to produce the best quality of biowaste, so special personalized attention shall be devoted to this customer.

It is advisable to design a survey model for this type of customer. It should be similar to that of the citizen, which is explained in Subclause 5.7.4.6.

It is important to take into account that there is no specific model of bin for the large producer to deposit the biowaste within their facilities. Each type of large producer has to check for the container that best suits their business.

Due to the amount of biowaste they generate and that this waste is heavy:

- No bags with biowaste weighing more than 20 kilograms should be lifted. If they generate more than that amount, they must be distributed in several bags with the maximum weight indicated.
- It should be made as easy as possible to ensure that the height of the biowaste dump at the collection point is as low as possible. With these criteria, the use of underground containers is appreciated by this type of customers as they have a low height to deposit the waste while preventing access to this type of waste once it has been deposited.
- If the collection point is on the public street, it is advisable to provide it with a lock so that the citizen does not contaminate the biowaste. Therefore, each large producer must be given a key to open the item at the collection point.

Recommended messages for large producers:

- Public markets as the heart of biowaste.
- Circular economy, the biowaste you recycle returns as a new product to the market.
- If they participate in the separation of biowaste it can be made a line of advertising through social networks, stickers in shops, etc. It is important to take this step if there is commitment and reality of recycling, so it is necessary to negotiate with these customers when to give them publicity. For example, when the collection point is at 50 % capacity. Giving large producers publicity before they have achieved their targets can be a disincentive for this type of project.

5.7.4.4 Associations in the neighborhood

These customers are, for example, cultural associations, senior citizens' clubs, women's associations and neighborhood meeting centers.

Associations are the gateway to citizens and in general it is easier to reach an association than a citizen, requiring fewer resources for the same task.

It is often the case that an association expects something in return for their participation. Therefore, if they get involved, they should be rewarded. The reward should be linked to biowaste (a compost bin, containers for the household, visits to the waste plant, etc.).

5.7.4.5 Training for municipal services in the area

These services comprise cleaning, collection, gardening, police services and others.

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Once the collection service has started in the area, they can inform the customer of incorrect behavior, so they have to be trained in:

- What is a biowaste?
- When this biowaste is collected.
- How this waste is deposited.
- What is done with this biowaste after it is collected.

These are very basic questions, but if they do not know how to answer them, it gives an image of disorganization at the municipality.

These operators must be informed of the communication channels established with customers (free hotline, social media, etc.) in case they do not know how to respond to customer concerns.

5.7.4.6 Citizens

The citizen is the most numerous customers in a given urban area, so they can provide a large amount of biowaste. The quality of the biowaste is more difficult to control, especially if the collection point is at the sidewalk, so the biopatrols should emphasize the message about how to obtain quality biowaste.

It is important to check the citizen's opinion before starting the biowaste collection service. The best tool for this is to carry out surveys in the street and online (participatory process of the City Council). These surveys should also be carried out with large producers.

Surveys should include the following information:

- a) Customer data: Type of customer, age, occupation, address, email. It is important to get the customer's email address. It is the basis to continue to be informed when the biopatrols disappear from the area.
- b) What do I do to minimize climate change? For example:
 - Reduce, reuse, recycle.
 - Reduce water consumption.
 - Reduce plastic consumption.
 - Sustainable purchasing.
 - Use of renewable energies.
- c) Do I currently separate waste? which ones? why?
- d) Are you willing to separate and deposit biowaste at the collection point? If not, please specify why not.
- e) What environmental benefits can be obtained from biowaste?
- f) Questions or suggestions.

The customer must previously accept the privacy conditions of the survey and it is advisable that the information is hosted on the portal of the City Council.

With this type of survey, previous information is obtained about what the customer thinks, an expected percentage of participation and there will be a database with the customer's emails for future communications. This is the information that will be used mainly to communicate with the customer after starting the biowaste collection service. If this information is not available, part of the follow-up of the next phase will not be possible.

There are two main motivations for citizens to recycle:

- Internal: they are usually environmental in nature and are stable over time. Thus, biopatrols must interact with customers through this type of motivations.
- External: they are usually economic. These motivations usually decrease when the economic incentive stops working.

Biowaste separation starts at home. According to VALUEWASTE surveys, the main reason for not separating biowaste at home is not finding the right space for biowaste separation.

One way to help in this regard is to deliver a bin to each household to deposit biowaste. Its characteristics are:

- No more than 10 liters if the biowaste is collected daily.
- It should be accompanied by a pack of biodegradable plastic bags. A quality biowaste is advisable to go inside this type of plastic.

Biopatrols should advise on how to place this container at home and what goes into it.

The delivery of this bin involves a great logistical effort, so it is advisable that the bin is delivered at the meeting point established in the area. This point will be attended by the biopatrols and its timetable will depend on the activity in the area.

At the time of delivery of the bin, the survey mentioned above will be made. If the customers do not want to do it at that moment, they will be told that they can do it whenever they want through the City Council's portal, indicating the web address.

Once the process has been completed, the bin collection areas should be analyzed. If the number of bins delivered in an area is low, it is advisable to carry out a visit by the biopatrols in that area and, if necessary, create a temporary bin drop-off point for that area.

Communication with the customer at this level is established by building or business.

The messages that should be launched for this type of customer are:

- Avoid food waste.
- Message: "everything that comes out of the earth returns to the earth".
- What is biowaste and what is not biowaste.
- Importance of the biodegradable bag.

6 Steps to follow after starting the collection

6.1 General

The day on which the biowaste collection service starts is an important day. If all of the above has not been taken into account, the quantity and quality of the biowaste may be low. And making changes is much more complicated at this stage of the project than at the previous one.

From this day on, the project must be monitored using the quantity and quality KPIs explained above.

The evolution of these two parameters will determine the actions to be taken in the future.

The actions to be carried out at this point must have the appropriate technology for an intelligent management of the information, based on the information obtained in the surveys prior to the collection. These actions come as follows:

6.2 Face-to-face actions

During the first week from the start of collection it is necessary for the biopatrols to establish face-to-face communication interaction with the customer to find out if they are participating in the separation of biowaste and, if they are not, to find out the reasons why.

At those collection points where there is a low quality and/or quantity of biowaste, the biopatrols should follow up in order to check the causes of the deviation. Information on the quality and quantity at the different collection points should be transmitted from the collection service to the biopatrols. There needs to be fluid communication between the collection and the awareness service.

6.3 Establish a meeting point

Inform the customer of the existence of a meeting point in their neighborhood and its opening hours. Normally it will coincide with the one in the previous phase.

6.4 Conducting surveys

In this phase, surveys should be carried out to analyze the degree of acceptance of the new service. These surveys should be carried out when the amount of biowaste collected has stabilized and will serve to gather new ideas with which to relaunch the selective collection of biowaste.

Surveys may be physical if biopatrols are in the area or using information contained in the database from previous surveys.

The contents of the surveys should focus on:

- Degree of acceptance of the new service. It is necessary to know if the customer continues to recycle biowaste.
- In the event that it does not continue, know why.
- What improvements would be necessary to incorporate more customers to this service?

6.5 Customer service hotlines

Due to economic reasons, the presence of biopatrols in the targeted area should be reduced as collection progresses. Their presence will only be necessary in those areas where the expected quantities/qualities are not achieved.

The use of personalized communication technologies is essential at this stage of the project.

Based on the information collected in the street by the biopatrols and the previous surveys, it is necessary to create a database of customers so that they are informed of the evolution of the project. An informed customer is a more participative customer.

Examples of best practices related to customer service are:

- To have its own website for biowaste, a website of active listening where you learn from customers. This website must be simple, resolve doubts and be linked to social networks.
- Use of social media:

- Try to keep the project alive. Create a lot of small news informing about the day to day of the project. It is better a lot of small news than a few big ones.
- If there are influencers in the area, it is interesting to contact them to add them to the project.
- Place a QR code at each biowaste collection point. This point leads to a web address where the customer is informed of the following:
 - Evolution of the quantity collected in the area and, if possible, at the collection point.
 - Quality evolution.
 - What is being done with the biowaste after it is collected.
 - Survey on participation in the project.
 - Other comments.

This information should be updated monthly and has to be transparent.

7 How to correct deviations

In any biowaste collection scheme, a contingency plan is necessary, especially if the results are not as expected for the two parameters considered: quantity and quality of the biowaste.

The communication process between the biopatrols and the biowaste collection service is essential. This collection service must inform at which service points there are quality and quantity deviations to the biopatrols.

The following aspects should be considered in this plan:

- a) Monthly monitor during 6 months after D-Day the Quantity and Quality KPI's. If the expected results are achieved, follow up every three months.
- b) If there is a new need for more collection points in the area, consider eliminating those with little biowaste.
- c) If at a collection point non-required waste appears constantly and in appreciable quantity, this collection point must be eliminated if the causes of this deviation cannot be solved.
- d) Face to face communication (biopatrols) where there is deviation in quantity and/or quality. If not, inform the customer through social networks and website.
- e) It is necessary to consider whether the collection point is adapted to the customer's needs.
- f) Inform to the customers of their actions where there are quantity and quality deviations using information as personalized as possible.
- g) As new areas are added to the collection, it is advisable to maintain comparative indicators between them.
- h) It is advisable to organize visits to the plant where the biowaste is treated so that customers can see what is done with it. In areas where there is less quantity/quality of biowaste, these visits are necessary.

8 Summary

In this Clause the key factors for the successful implementation of urban biowaste selective collection schemes are summarised.

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One of the most important steps is to establish a day (D-day) for the beginning of the selective collection of biowaste in an area. Actions can be then divided in two: before and after this day.

Before D-day:

- Establish quality and quantity KPIs of collected biowaste.
- Identify large customers in the area, they are the key to obtain a high quality and quantity biowaste.
- Make a proposal for the physical location of the new biowaste collection points. The priority is to place them beside the other selective collection bins (light packaging, paper, glass, etc.).
- The collection point must be adapted to the type of customer:
 - citizen, lid no more than 25 × 25 cm;
 - large producer: lid of at least 40 × 40 cm with key opening and the lowest possible discharge height.
- Communicate the proposals of this initial plan to those interested and listen to them. Make changes to the proposal if applicable.

Once the proposal is known, the communication process starts. Its characteristics are:

- There must be a personal a direct interaction with the customers (biopatrols).
- It has an order, going from the particular to the general: schools, large producers, associations, municipal services and citizens.
- In this phase, try to collect as much information as possible about customers: name, e-mail, address, dates, etc. Create your own database of customers. Online surveys are a good tool to obtain this information.

After D-day:

- Start monitoring and using KPIs designed before.
- During the first week, biopatrols must establish a face-to-face communication with the customer to know if they are participating and if not, find out why not.
- Establish surveys and customer service hotlines to analyze the degree of acceptance of the new service.
- If there are KPI's deviations use biopatrols to know why. In this case the communication between the biowaste collection service and the biopatrols is essential.
- Inform to the customer of the result of the biowaste collection, using the information from the database created at the stage before.

Annex A (informative)

Optimal biowaste typology

The following waste fractions can be considered as biowaste:

- Fruit and vegetables scrap.
- Cooked food leftovers.
- Eggshells, shellfish and nuts.
- Coffee grounds and infusions.

The main characteristic of this waste is that it occupies little volume, has a high amount of water and if the temperature is high, it decomposes quickly generating leachates and odors.

The density of the biowaste that is deposited in the biowaste bin depends on its quality. According to VALUEWASTE experience, the average density of the biowaste in the biowaste bin is about 350 kg/m³.

An effective communication campaign should explain what a biowaste is and which biowaste should not be managed in a biowaste collection (non-required waste) like:

- Dirty paper towels and napkins.
- Wipes.
- Diapers
- Pet excrement.
- Pruning and vegetable waste. Although classified as a biowaste, they should not be introduced into the collection point as their volume and different composition affect the subsequent treatments to be carried out. This waste should be collected using another collection system.

“This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No. 818312”.

Co-funded by the Horizon 2020 programme
of the European Union